

“THE IMPORTANCE OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN MANAGING THE QUALITY OF EDUCATION IN PUBLIC SCHOOLS”

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7852646>

Dushabayev Abdulla Musayevich

Jizzax politexnika instituti, Xorijiy tillar kafedrasida o'qituvchisi

dushabayevabdulla8727@gmail.com

Abstract: This article advances ideas about the main importance of digital technologies in managing the quality of education in public schools, as well as digital technology is developing widely in our education system. Obviously, it is necessary to establish the targeted use of new digital technologies in the educational process. Modern society is characterized by the active use of the world Information Network, which is not limited in size and speed of information transmission.

Keywords: information, digital technology, e-learning, electron books, computers, modern education, electron library

Introduction

Today, it is difficult to imagine the educational process without computers and digital technology like in all areas. This does not mean that the use of the capabilities of computer and digital technology solves the solution of all issues, that is, the transmission and processing of information - this guarantees the complete formation of knowledge, skills and skills, since all this is considered to be only one of the effective additional way of training.

Digital technologies are developing at a tremendous speed. Many areas of activity are switching to digital systems: hospitals, catering establishments, educational institutions. In the modern era, when the speed of obtaining and using information has greatly increased, in our opinion, it is impossible to improve the quality of education and educate socially active youth without introducing digital technologies into the education system. Previously, we conducted educational programs in the traditional way in the form of lectures. This was also done with the help of voluminous books and manuals. This, in turn, did not provide such a high quality of education. Students were forced to carry large bags of literature and large bags with a hood to master various additional materials. Now the process of digitization of education has begun.

Discussions and results

That is why the use of modern digital technology in the educational system is carried out in the following areas:

Digital and communication technologies as an object of study, that is, pupils in the process of obtaining knowledge will receive general understanding and qualifications in the field of new information technologies, including computer, multimedia, Distance

Learning, Internet technologies and their components, as well as in the field of use; as a means of teaching digital technologies, that is, on the basis of modern information and pedagogical technologies, pupils are given knowledge, that is, digital technologies are used in the teaching of general education and specialist subjects. Lecture, practical and laboratory classes are organized on the basis of modern software tools of computers, while interdisciplinary integration is carried out; as a means of managing the educational process, i.e., the creation of a system of informatization analysis and forecasting on the basis of information and communication technologies and its involvement in practice in improving the effectiveness of educational, spiritual and educational and scientific research activities of the educational institution. In the educational process at the school, students learn to work with text using computer, create visual objects and a database, use spreadsheets. Students learn new ways of collecting information, their use, their worldview expands. The use of computer in classes increases motivation for reading, pupils' curiosity, the effectiveness of independent work. Together with the computer, the computer offers new opportunities in the field of education, in the reading and creativity of pupils. For the first time, a situation arises when an educational computer becomes the main instrument of the future profession of an individual. Education will indeed enter our lives throughout life's career.

When applying the act, it is necessary to try to realize all the abilities of the individual – curiosity, decency, creativity, communication and aesthetic abilities. In order for these abilities to come true to the proper high level, it is necessary for the pedagogue to be knowledgeable in the computer field. It is necessary to start the development of this knowledge in educators during their studies in public educational institutions. Knowledge in the field of computer can be expressed by: the ability to evaluate experience in a modern information environment and apply it in activities: to try to develop personal creativity skills: the presence of experience and theoretical knowledge in the organization of general communicative Culture, Information Exchange: the acquisition, selection, storage, processing, transformation, presentation, transmission and application of information.

Nowadays, it is clear to everyone that the child is faced with a computer at every step – at home, in Internet clubs. The natural question arises: is all the child also purposefully using this modern technology in its place? What measures are required to do this?

It is known that in secondary schools of our country, a special educational discipline was introduced so that pupils can learn information technology, mainly in the 5th – 7th grade, that is, at the age of 12-16 years.

In particular, the computerization of Education does not consist only in providing the school with the necessary equipment and computer, first of all, it provides for an increase in the work productivity of teachers and pupils, the effectiveness of Education. Nowadays, it is precisely the search for psychologically-pedagogically new

approaches to mental education that is growing in importance. The development of mental activity of children in the educational process is directly related to the use of various forms and methods of Education.

Now, determining the exact possibilities of using computer technologies in the process of primary education, which are increasingly taking a deeper place in our lives, in-depth study of the pedagogical, physiological, hygienic and medical foundations of this process, the introduction of advanced experiments in the educational system of developed countries in this area into the practice of Uzbek education is considered from. The use of digital technologies in the educational process in the educational process – certain conditions for youngsters should be available, namely Information Resources computer, video projector, multimedia tools, printer, scanner and modern software tools.

Today, in improving the efficiency of the educational process, the main component of computer and digital technology tools: educational programs, multimedia technologies, educational uslu-biy supply of distance learning, a virtual laboratory, an electronic textbook, an electronic educational library, international internet systems, will become important and relevant. The effectiveness and excellence of the learning process will depend on how the information is given to the learner, how it is perceived by them and how it is put into practice. Multimedia technologies describe each information about the pedagogical and economic processes under study to educators in action, voice and video views. This, while saving the time it takes to provide large volumes of information, increases the level of their acceptance and practical use of new information. In other words, for the perfect use of computer and digital technology in the educational process, the main focus should be primarily on creating the conditions necessary for the teacher and the pupil, the effective application of computers in educational processes, that is, the widespread use of multimedia electronic educational and methodological manuals.

These views and views are also confirmed in the research of foreign scientists. A number of foreign researchers who have studied the importance of digital technology in the education of the younger generation believe that in the process of moving to a new information stage of the development of society, it is necessary to form skills and competencies in the younger generation, such as rational use of technical means, reception, processing and use of information, perception of the universe Also, the triggers note that it is necessary to form the psychological preparation of children for the digital environment from the early school period. This requires downloading qualitatively new requirements for primary education, which is considered the first stage of school education, in which the computer literacy of children is increased. After all, information technology allows you to raise a child as a creative person in harmony with traditional educational tools. Training-methodological support A new generation of training and methodical provision.

As in all areas, the results of the progress of Science in the educational system, as well as the introduction of modern computer tools, lead to a rapid renewal of knowledge in various fields of science. Learners are required to use different forms of educational literature so that they can quickly master new knowledge today, when the amount of information is increasing. The content of educational literature should ensure the formation of independent and free thinking, improvement of the acquired knowledge, the formation of skills for tracing new knowledge from various educational literatures in educators.

E-learning literature is a resource based on modern digital technology that has the capacity to aggregate, describe, update, Store, provide and control knowledge in an interactive way. In the educational process of the system of continuing education, the following types of educational literature are used: textbook, tutorial, dictionary, annotated dictionary, dataset, lecture course, lecture set, methodological instruction, methodological manual, review, digest, electronic textbook, Data Bank, etc.

An electronic textbook is a basic educational electronic product based on new information and computer technologies and fully compatible with the educational discipline (or several disciplines) of specialties and areas of the state educational standard, created at a high scientific and methodological level. An electronic tutorial is an electronic product approved by educational institutions as a partial or complete replacement of a textbook, or as a complement and guide. The purpose of the electronic textbook creation technologies course is to provide pupils with information about the process of creating electronic textbooks, in which the procedure, requirements, organizers and software tools used in the creation of electronic textbooks and the qualifications for their use are improved. With the development of Science and technology in the system of continuing education, the preparation of electronic educational literature in general and special subjects, the content of which is rapidly changing, deepened, has a good effect in the teaching process.

E-learning literature will be focused on expanding the imagination of learners, developing their initial knowledge, and providing additional information. The most basic representative of the e-learning literature is the e-textbook. Electronic textbook-intended for the application of a teaching style based on computer technology, Independent Education and comprehensive effective assimilation of educational materials and scientific information related to science: educational and scientific materials only in verbal (text) form; - educational materials in verbal (text) and two-dimensional graphic form; multimedia (multimedia - multi-informational environment) applications, i.e. information in three-dimensional graphic representation, in voice, video, animation and partial verbal (text) form;

tactile (perceptible, perceptible) in nature, expressed in a form that makes the learner penetrate the real world, in which his stereo copies are depicted in the world of the computer screen, and create his imagination in relation to the objects in it. An electronic textbook is based on universal software, which provides information,

knowledge of certain professional activities and provides information about acquired knowledge. The broad-sense explanatory interpretation of most of the concepts associated with e-learning literature is complemented by knowledge that is expanding further as computer and information technology develop. Therefore, comments on the main concepts and terms associated with the creation and use of electronic educational literature are presented in the following comments.. An experimental-applied automated system is a complex of technical and programmatic tools that provide for experimental work, and experimental research directly using physical objects and or mathematical models. An electronic publication is a compilation consisting of graphic, textual, digital, colloquial, musical, videophoto and other information objects In one electronic publication, information sources, information processing, management structure may be allocated. An electronic edition can be executed on any electronic carrier, and can also be printed on an electronic computer network.

The Electronic Library is a programmatic complex with a private system of documentation and security for students and educators, providing the possibility of concentrating and communicating full-text E-information on the basis of resources, telecommunication tools.

Electronic control (testing) is a component of e - learning publication, an analogue of traditional computer-free testing. In the case of electronic testing, the computer displays the test and its results, introducing algorithms related to it. (For example, the presence or absence opportunity to return to completed or missed assignments, the limitation of time to one test, etc.).

Conclusion.

Digital technology phase is a programmatic telecommunications environment based on the management of educators, teachers and educational institutions and the use of computerized techniques that provide society with unified technological means of information provision. This environment is designed to support the management of the educational process and educational institution with information, informatization of the progress and results of the educational process, as well as non-educational activities.

Electronic assignments are an important manifestation of the source of information, which embodies the set of tasks that the teacher arranges for independent and supervisory work, taking into account the individual capabilities of the teachers. The assignments created can be recommended to learners in their traditional "paper" and electronic variants. An electronic tool is a tool that allows participants in the educational process to develop, modify, bind, transmit, distance, store and perform other active actions on information agents.is the process of ensuring the field of education with the theory and practice of the development and use of modern information technologies designed to introduce the psychological and pedagogical goals of training and education. It also ensures that we occupy an

important place in the global community. Today's classrooms are very different from decades ago, and classrooms are equipped with computers, iPads, tablets, smart boards and other types of educational technologies. As elsewhere in the world, seven digital generation screens have appeared in Uzbekistan and are being used to improve image quality - a TV, a computer, a tablet, a phablet, a smartphone and a smart watch.

REFERENCES:

1. Sharon Y.V. Digitalization of technologies in higher and professional education: from personality-oriented smart didactics to blockchain in network training of specialists // modern problems of science and education. – 2019. – № 2. Abdullaev M., Saidakhror, G., & # (2020). Digital economy-current areas of personnel training. Archive of Scientific Research, 1(23). discovery <https://journal.tsue.uz/index.php/archive/article/view/2702> . 3. <https://community.uzbekcoders.uz/post/raqamli-texnologiyalar-609525917>